

1 **An HPV16 infection model in primary human keratinocytes.**

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7 Papillomavirus infection systems are technically challenging. We measured total transcription at 7 days in
8 primary human keratinocytes following infection with HPV type 16. We demonstrate here activation of a
9 set of genes representative of events occurring early in the primary phase of infection. This included
10 activation of *Podxl2* and kinetochore component *Zwint*, silencing of interferon pathway component *Ifrd1*,
11 and induction of the homeobox *Ybx2* and the nuclear factor *Zfr2*. We demonstrate here that cells undergo
12 a proliferative increase during the early phase of papillomavirus infection characterized by Tk1
13 activation. We detected induction of *l12rb2* during HPV16 infection. Papillomavirus infection was marked
14 by intermediate filament *NEFH* induction.

15 Citations

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